

Studies in the Synthesis of Furocoumarins: Part XXII: Synthesis of 7H-Furo [3,2-f] [1] benzopyran-7-one

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6-Hydroxycoumarin, on allylation followed by Claisen migration, gave 6-hydroxy-5-allylcoumarin (Ic), structure of which was confirmed by its N.M.R. spectrum. (Ic) was converted to (IIa) by treatment with osmium tetroxide followed by cyclisation with o-phosphoric acid. (IIb) was obtained by treating (Ic) with conc. sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (10%).

SYNTHESIS of Furocoumarins from hydroquinone and its derivatives having alkyl substituents on furan and coumarin rings have been reported by Kaufman *et al.*^{2,3}. We report here the synthesis of 7H-furo[2,3-f][1] benzopyran-7-one (IIa) and its 2-methyl derivative (IIb) for evaluating their psoralene like photosensitising activity.

6-Hydroxycoumarin⁴ (Ia) was converted to its allyl ether (Ib), which underwent Claisen rearrangement in boiling dimethyl aniline to give 5-allyl-6-hydroxycoumarin (Ic). The structure of (Ic) was confirmed by NMR spectrum (CDCl₃): δ 9.5, 1H singlet, hydroxylic proton, at 6-position: δ 7.17 and δ 7.0, 2H, doublets, ($J = 8$ Hz), H₇ and H₈ (aromatic), δ 6.35 and δ 7.95, 2H, doublets ($J = 10$ Hz), at H₃ and H₄, δ 6.1-5.7, 1H multiplet, =CH, δ 5.1 and δ 4.82, 2H, multiplet = CH₂, showing barely visible long range coupling ($J = 1$ Hz): δ 3.62, 2H, doublet, -CH₂-CH =. The two proton doublets at δ 7.17 and δ 7.0 indicates the two aromatic proton at H₇ and H₈ are free to couple. If it were 7-allyl-6-hydroxycoumarin, NMR spectrum would have shown two singlet for proton at H₅ and H₈. (Ic), on treatment with osmium tetroxide⁵ and potassium periodate gave 5-formyl methyl-6-hydroxycoumarin (Id), which was not isolated but cyclised directly with o-phosphoric acid to give the title compound (IIa)⁶. (Ic),

when triturated with conc. sulphuric acid^{6,7} gave 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-7H-furo [3,2-f] [1] benzopyran-7-one (III), which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal in boiling diphenyl ether furnished 2-methyl-7H-furo [3,2-f] [1] benzopyran-7-one (IIb).

Experimental

Ultraviolet spectra were recorded on Beckmann DU-2 Model, IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 457 model and NMR spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 Model using TMS as an internal indicator.

6-Allyloxycoumarin (Ib) :

A mixture of 6-hydroxycoumarin (5 g.), allyl bromide (5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (100 ml.) for 10 hr. After the evaporation of acetone, the residue was treated with water. The compound was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide, dried and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 90°. Yield 3 g. (Found: C, 71.58; H, 4.83. C₁₂H₁₀O₃ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.95%). IR spectra (Nujol): 1720 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl > C = O group), 1265 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ether linkage).

6-Hydroxy-5-allylcoumarin (Ic) :

6-Allyloxycoumarin (2 g.), and dimethylaniline (15-20 ml.) were refluxed for 6 hr in nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was poured into ice and hydrochloric acid. The product was treated with sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. The dried residue was purified by passing it over a short column of alumina using chloroform as eluent. It crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 172°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 71.19; H, 4.80. C₁₂H₁₀O₃ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.95%). IR spectra (Nujol) 1680 cm⁻¹ (lactonyl > C = O group).

I a, R = R₁ = H

b, R = Allyl, R₁ = H

c, R = H, R₁ = Allyl

d, R = H, R₁ = -CH₂CHO

II a, R = H

b, R = CH₃

7-H-Furo[3,2-f][1]benzopyran-7-one (IIa) :

A solution of 6-hydroxy-5-allylcoumarin (0.5 g.) in ethyl acetate was vigorously shaken with 50 mg. osmium tetroxide in water (100 ml.). Potassium periodate (2 g. in 100 ml. water) was added during the period of 2 hr. Ethyl acetate layer was separated, dried and evaporated. The residue was dissolved in benzene and passed over alumina. Evaporation of solvent left a residue. This was heated with *o*-phosphoric acid (5 ml.) on a water bath at 70°-80° for 1½ hr. The contents were poured into ice water. The product was extracted with ethyl acetate, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and finally purified by chromatographing over alumina using benzene as eluent. It crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 231°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 71.44; H, 3.67. $C_{11}H_8O_3$ requires C, 70.98; H, 3.22%). IR spectra (Nujol) 1740 cm^{-1} (lactonyl > C = O group) 890 cm^{-1} (furan). λ_{max}^{MeOH} , 252 and 300 nm (log ϵ , 3.96 and 3.64).

2-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-7H-furo[3,2-f][1] benzopyran-7-one (III) :

6-Hydroxy-5-allylcoumarin (1 g.) was triturated with concentrated sulphuric acid (6 ml.) for 1 hr at room temperature. The contents were poured into ice water. The separated product was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove original compound and finally crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 104°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 71.27; H, 4.84. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.95%).

2-Methyl-7H-furo [3,2-f] [1] benzopyran-7-one (IIb) :

A mixture of 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-7H-furo(3,2-f) (1) benzopyran-7-one (0.5 g.), palladised charcoal (10%; 0.3 g.) and diphenyl ether (5 ml.) was refluxed for 20 hr. Reaction mixture was filtered hot and the product separated on cooling. It crystallised from diphenyl ether, m.p. 161°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 71.58; H, 3.84. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.00; H, 4.00%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} , 318 nm (log ϵ 4.20).

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